

Na-BatB Data Management Plan for P2-type NMO Cathode with Improved Stability for Sustainable Na-ion Batteries

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the strategy for collecting, managing, storing, sharing, and preserving research data generated within the Na-BatB project. The project aims to develop a sustainable, water-based, and volatile organic compound (VOC)-free sodium-ion battery (SIB) electrode preparation process using P2-type layered transition metal oxide (TMO) cathode materials. The DMP covers experimental data from four work packages: project management and dissemination (WP1), synthesis of P2-type layered Na-ion cathodes (WP2), cathode material coating (WP3), and wet electrode preparation (WP4). Data types include electrochemical characterization data, structural and compositional characterization data, microscopy images, spectroscopic data, and electrode processing data. All data will be managed in accordance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and will be deposited in the open-access repository Zenodo. This DMP is a living document and will be updated as the project progresses. It was created using the ARGOS platform with the Latvian Council of Science Blueprint template, and datasets are described using the LCS FARP form.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

P2-Na-Bat: P2-type NMO Cathode with Improved Stability for Sustainable Na-ion

Batteries

Researchers

Dr. Gints Kucinskis, Dr. Gunars Bajars, Dr. Vitalijs Lazarenko, Dr. Einars Sprogis, Rita Leimane, Undergraduate Student 2 (TBC)

Organizations

Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia (ISSP UL)

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Na-BatB Data Management Plan for P2-type NMO Cathode with Improved Stability for Sustainable Na-ion Batteries

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Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia (ISSP UL)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: P2-Na-Bat: P2-type NMO Cathode with Improved Stability for Sustainable Na-ion Batteries

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2026-02-27

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

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sharing, and preserving research data generated within the Na-Bat_B project. The project aims to

develop a sustainable, water-based, and volatile organic compound (VOC)-free sodium-ion battery

(SIB) electrode preparation process using P2-type layered transition metal oxide (TMO) cathode

materials.

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characterization data, structural and compositional characterization data, microscopy images,

spectroscopic data, and electrode processing data. All data will be managed in accordance with

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This DMP is a living document and will be updated as the project progresses. It was created using

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Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data in the Na-BatB project is generated to achieve the following scientific objectives:

WP2 – Synthesis and characterization: To optimize the synthesis of P2-type Na₂/3MO₂ (NMO) layered transition metal oxide cathode materials through

iterative structural, compositional, and electrochemical characterization, targeting 600 Wh/kg specific energy and 1000 full charge-discharge cycles until $\text{SoH} \geq 80\%$.

WP3 – Coating development: To develop and characterize inert protective coatings (Al_2O_3 , MgO , SiO_2) on active cathode material via wet-chemical methods, improving stability in air and water, and enabling aqueous electrode processing.

WP4 – Aqueous electrode preparation: To develop and validate a VOC-free, water-based electrode preparation process using aqueous binders (CMC/SBR, Na alginate, CMC/NaPAA), and to demonstrate the resulting electrodes in full Na-ion battery cells with performance comparable to PVDF/NMP baseline.

WP1 – Dissemination: To support open-access publications and conference contributions. At least 3 Q1/Q2 peer-reviewed publications are planned, and all associated data will be deposited in Zenodo.

All data generation serves the overarching goal of demonstrating TRL4 Na-ion battery cathode technology that is both high-performance (180 Wh/kg on stack level, 600 Wh/kg on cathode material level, 1000 full charge-discharge cycles until $\text{SoH} \geq 80\%$) and genuinely sustainable (VOC-free, PFAS-free production). The project starts at TRL2 and finishes at TRL4.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No pre-existing datasets from other projects or databases are planned for direct re-use within Na-BatB. All data will be generated anew within the project. However, the project will reference published literature data and data from the group's previous projects (NoVOC, InCoatBat) for context and comparison, without formally incorporating those datasets. If any existing public datasets (e.g., crystallographic data from ICDD PDF or ICSD databases) are referenced, this will be noted in the metadata.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Battery researchers and materials scientists: electrochemical and structural data on P2-type Na-ion cathodes, protective coatings, and aqueous electrode processing, particularly for Na-ion battery communities where open machine-readable data following BIG-MAP/LC-BAT5 standards is currently scarce.

Manufacturers and industry: data on scalable, sustainable electrode preparation processes (VOC-free, PFAS-free) relevant for battery cell production.

Standards bodies and policy-makers: data supporting the development of regulations on sustainable battery manufacturing (EU Battery Regulation).

Educational institutions: data as teaching material for battery science and electrochemistry courses.

General public: project results will be communicated through ISSP social media and public events (Night of Researchers, etc.).

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema / Dublin Core / BIG-MAP

<https://schema.datacite.org>

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

IUPAC nomenclature; BIG-MAP / LC-BAT5 keywords

<https://iupac.org>

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

Sample ID convention: NaB-WP-[sample type]-[batch]-[experiment number] (e.g., NaB-WP2-NMO-001-GCD01)

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Metadata will follow DataCite Metadata Schema and Dublin Core standards, consistent with BIG-MAP and LC-BAT5 consortium recommendations for battery research data. Metadata will be structured to enable harvesting and indexing by Zenodo and OpenAIRE. README files will accompany each deposited dataset describing experimental conditions, methodology, units, and file structure. Keywords include: sodium-ion battery, Na-ion battery, P2-type cathode, NMO, Na₂/3MnO₂, protective coating, aqueous electrode processing, VOC-free battery manufacturing, PFAS-free electrode, electrochemical characterization, XRD, XPS, SEM, TEM, Raman spectroscopy, ICP-AES, ISSP UL, Latvia.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Research data will be made openly available (Open Access) as a rule, following the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. A temporary embargo of up to 12 months may be applied on a dataset-by-dataset basis to allow for scientific publication or intellectual property assessment. All embargoed data will be made publicly available no later than at the time of project completion (M36). During the

embargo period, access can be granted upon reasonable request to the PI (Dr. Gints Kucinskis, gints.kucinskis@cfi.lu.lv).

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

A temporary embargo of up to 12 months may be applied on a dataset-by-dataset basis to allow for scientific publication or intellectual property assessment. All embargoed datasets will be made publicly available no later than at project completion (M36).

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Most data can be accessed with standard software: Microsoft Excel or LibreOffice Calc (.xlsx, .csv), text editors (.txt), OriginPro or free OriginViewer (.opj). XRD data (.brml, .raw) may require Bruker DIFFRAC.EVA or free software (VESTA, GSAS-II, PowderCell). Electron microscopy images (.tif/.jpg) are readable by any image viewer. XPS data (.spe) may require Thermo Fisher Avantage; exported .txt versions will also be provided.

VESTA / GSAS-II / OriginPro / Bruker DIFFRAC.EVA

Latest available

<https://jp-minerals.org/vesta/en/>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

Each deposited dataset on Zenodo will include a README.txt or README.md file containing: experimental conditions, sample identification, equipment specifications, measurement parameters, software versions used for data acquisition and analysis, units of measurement, and variable definitions. This documentation enables independent validation and re-use of the data.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Common open file formats (.xlsx, .csv, .txt) are used alongside instrument-native formats to maximize accessibility. All quantitative data uses SI units. Metadata follows DataCite Metadata Schema and Dublin Core standards. XRD data provided in both instrument format (.brml, .raw) and open .xy format. XPS data provided in both .spe and exported .txt format. Electron microscopy images in .tif/.jpg. These formats are open and compatible with widely available free software.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

BIG-MAP / LC-BAT5 ontology; IUPAC nomenclature; SI units; DataCite; Dublin Core

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

Qualified references to related datasets (e.g., from NoVOC or InCoatBat projects) will be included in Zenodo metadata where the data directly relates to or builds upon those datasets. Interoperability standards applied: BIG-MAP and LC-BAT5 ontology and data schema recommendations for battery materials research; Dublin Core and DataCite metadata standards; SI units throughout all quantitative data; IUPAC nomenclature for chemical compounds and processes.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY 4.0 permits the widest possible reuse, allowing others to share and adapt the material for any purpose, provided that appropriate credit is given to the original creators. This is consistent with open science principles promoted by the Latvian Council of Science and Horizon Europe.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Data will be usable by third parties via Zenodo (DOI-referenced) with minimum 20-year preservation (Zenodo policy). ISSP UL will maintain metadata and contact information after project completion.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-03

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2046-03-03

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

All experimental work will be recorded in electronic lab notebooks maintained by the PI and team members, including batch numbers, synthesis parameters, equipment settings, and calibration data. Samples will be assigned unique identifiers (NaB-WP-[sample type]-[batch]-[experiment number]). Electrochemical measurements will be performed in triplicate where feasible. Structural characterization (XRD, XPS) will include calibration/reference measurements. All datasets will be reviewed by Dr. Kucinskis before deposition on Zenodo. Data files will be provided in both raw and converted open formats. README files will accompany each deposited dataset.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs related to data management, open access publication charges, and Zenodo deposition are covered from the project budget. Zenodo is free of charge for standard deposits. Open access publication fees (6,000 EUR allocated in the project budget) will cover CC BY publication in Q1/Q2 journals. Alternatively, preprints will be deposited on arXiv. Staff time for data curation, metadata preparation, and deposition is embedded in the personnel costs of the project. No additional external storage costs are anticipated.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Gints Kucinskis (0000-0001-9432-2358)

Dr. Gints Kucinskis (PI) is responsible for overall data management, reviewing and approving all datasets before deposition on Zenodo. Day-to-day data recording and lab notebook maintenance is performed by Dr. Vitalijs Lazarenko (post-doc), Dr. Einars Sprugis (post-doc), and student researchers. All data management follows FAIR principles and the procedures described in this DMP.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Long-term preservation is ensured by Zenodo (CERN), which commits to maintaining data for at least 20 years at no cost to depositors. ISSP UL will maintain access to metadata and contact information for the project after completion. No additional costs for long-term preservation are anticipated after project completion. Zenodo is funded through CERN and OpenAIRE, ensuring sustainability without depositor fees.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

During the project, all data will be stored on the ISSP UL institutional network storage system, maintained by the ISSP IT department with daily automatic

backups and access controls. Key data will be redundantly stored on Microsoft OneDrive (institutional subscription). Workstations connected to the ISSP network are protected by institutional IT security measures (firewall, antivirus, access controls). Electronic lab notebooks and data files are organized in a shared folder on the ISSP institutional server accessible only to project team members. Upon finalization of datasets, they are deposited on Zenodo for long-term preservation and public access. Zenodo's infrastructure (CERN data centers) ensures high availability and redundancy.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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